

Example Data Management Plan – complete version with full responses

A novel library of tagged transcription factors in *Drosophila*

Data Stewardship Wizard (DSW) Example Data Management Plan

Complete version with full responses

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Based on

Based on Standard DMP template for Biotechnology and Biological Sciences Research Council (BBSRC) 2024

Funded by the [ELIXIR-UK: FAIR Data Stewardship training UKRI award \(MR/V038966/1\)](#) and [BioFAIR](#)

(Q1) Proposal name

A novel library of tagged transcription factors in *Drosophila*

(Q2) Description of the data: Type of study

We will generate a collection of transgenic fly lines in which transcription factors have been GFP tagged using CRISPR. The tissue distribution of 150 unstudied transcription factors will be mapped by imaging the GFP tag using confocal microscopy in three tissues and two developmental stages.

(Q3) Description of the data: Types of data

The project will create non-human (*Drosophila melanogaster*) data exclusively. Generated data types are:

- **Sequence data:** sequences of empty vectors and sequences of inserts (homology arms and guide RNAs).
- **Genomic information:** related to generated fly lines (Genomic location of CRISPR modifications, inserted construct, associated gene, identity and relative location of the inserted tag, genotype of the injected fly line).
- **Confocal images with associated metadata:** (sample data such as tissue, developmental stage, antibodies used, etc. and technical metadata such as microscope hardware, objective used, laser intensity, etc.) and data analysis.

(Q4) Description of the data: Origin of the data

The study will generate original primary data.

Gene models and genomic coordinates will be according to FlyBase (flybase.org) genome version R6.58.

(Q5) Description of the data: Format and scale of the data

- **Sequence data:** sequences of empty vectors in genbank format and sequences of inserts in FASTA format (text files). The total size will be less than 100 MB
- **Genomic data:** Genome and insert information in FlyBase stock ontology (OWL 2 Web Ontology Language) format. The total size will be less than 1GB.
- **Confocal microscopy:** Confocal stacks will be captured in CZI, a proprietary Zeiss format and stored as both CZI and OME-TIFF. On average, we will produce 20 confocal stacks per TF and we will analyse the expression 200 TFs. We anticipate that the total size of confocal data will be around 500 GB

(Q6) Managing, storing and curating data

Raw and analysed images will be stored and curated on a dedicated server (costed for in the project) with backup in the cloud (Google Drive). Confocal image file names will be stereotyped and contain date, transcription factor ID, tissue and developmental stage information.

(Q7) Metadata standards and data documentation

Confocal microscopy technical metadata (Microscope hardware, Image acquisition settings) will be stored as OME-XML (docs.openmicroscopy.org/ome-model/5.6.3/ome-xml/).

Biological metadata (organism, strain, developmental stage, sex, tissue and genotype) will be stored in Experimental Factor Ontology (EFO) (format.ebi.ac.uk/efo/). Analyses (description of tissue expression patterns) will be stored in Flybase Fly Anatomy (FBbt) format, a structured controlled vocabulary of the anatomy of *Drosophila melanogaster* (github.com/FlyBase/drosophila-anatomy-developmental-ontology).

(Q8) Data preservation strategy and standards

All research data will be kept locally for a minimum of 10 years after the end of the project. Longer-term data preservation will be achieved by depositing the data to public repositories

(Q9) Where will data be shared?

All data will be available through a web interface to the dedicated server. In addition, data will be available through existing, dedicated databases:

- **Sequence data:** sequences of empty vectors will be submitted to genbank.
- **Genomic information:** related to generated fly lines will be submitted to FlyBase (see letter of support)
- **Confocal microscopy:** Published images will be submitted to the BioImage Archive (ebi.ac.uk/bioimage-archive/). Data analyses (identified tissue distributions) will be submitted to flybase

(Q10) When will data be available?

All data will be made available upon generation through our dedicated server and public repositories.

(Q11) How will data be made findable and accessible?

All data and rich metadata will be available through a web interface to the dedicated server. In addition, data will be available through the public repositories. The resource will be published in a preprint journal early in the project. We will publicise the database at meetings and through our network of collaborators and board members. Digital Object Identifiers pointing to the data will be published on our server and in any publications.

(Q12) How will data be made reusable?

Metadata will be collected as described above and made available through our server and dedicated public repositories

(Q13) Restrictions or delays to sharing, with planned actions to limit such restrictions

No human, sensitive, proprietary or patentable data will be produced or used in this study. We do not foresee any restrictions or delays in data sharing.

(Q14) Secondary use

The European *Drosophila* Society (europeandrosophilasociety.org) lists 370 labs Europe-wide of which more than one quarter (109) are based in the UK. The research foci of the UK fly community are widely spread and range from evolution and population genetics to physiology and disease models. Transcriptional control is one of the main determinants of cellular function, and thus stands at the epicentre of biological research. Our resource will allow *Drosophila* researchers from diverse scientific backgrounds to study TFs of their choosing in any context. This resource will serve as a blueprint for similar efforts for different gene families or in different model organisms. Furthermore, the tissue distribution of 150 previously unstudied transcription factors will encourage researchers to look further than the usual, well-studied genes.

(Q15) Formal information/data security standards

The University is ISO 27001 certified.

(Q16) Main risks to data security

Only model organism data will be generated.

(Q17) Capabilities

The university provides unlimited storage capacity on Google Drive as well as access to Arkivum for long-term storage of large datasets.

Furthermore, the university provides a free platform to share the intellectual products of the university freely and openly with the staff and students of the university or with the global academic and public community (RADAR).

As indicated in the Justification of Resources, a server has been costed in the project to provide medium-term storage and analysis capabilities.

(Q18) Maintaining and implementing the Data Management Plan

The data management plan will be updated throughout the life-time of the project. Data management plan implementation, auditing and revision is the responsibility of the PI and will be a recurring topic during the weekly team meetings.

(Q19) Environmental considerations

Environmental sustainability at the University is guided by the framework of our externally certified ISO14001:2015 Environmental Management System (EMS). The EMS enforces an environmental policy that sets out our principles and goals, and is supported by a series of strategies outlining our key vision, drivers and objectives for each key aspect of environmental sustainability. The university also takes part in the LEAF initiative to reduce the carbon emissions of research labs and create an environment that supports research quality

(Q20) Responsibilities

Person responsible for:

- **Study-wide data management:** Unnamed PDRA (new hire for this project)
- **Metadata creation:** Unnamed PDRA (new hire for this project)
- **Data security:** PI
- **Quality assurance of data:** PI and University Research Data Manager